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1 **New Solid Phase Microextraction Fibers with Green Clay Coating via Radio Frequency**

2 **Magnetron Sputtering for Detecting Low-polar Compounds in Water Samples**

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1 Abstract

2 **Background:** Developing highly sensitive and selective measurement techniques to detect trace
3 compounds in diverse matrices is a significant challenge in analytical chemistry. These techniques
4 must adhere to green chemistry principles by minimizing organic solvent use, simplifying sample
5 preparation, and streamlining process steps. Additionally, there is a growing need for sustainable
6 analytical methods due to increased environmental awareness. The problem addressed in this work is
7 the need for an eco-friendly and efficient method for the extraction and detection of trace
8 organochlorine pesticides in water samples.

9 **Results:** We employed SPME using a novel clay thin film sorbent, deposited on a nickel-titanium
10 alloy wire via magnetron sputtering. Montmorillonite clay was chosen for its excellent adsorption
11 properties and eco-friendly nature, aligning with green chemistry principles. The approach involved
12 coating the SPME fiber with hydrophobic modified montmorillonite clay, followed by silylation. The
13 method was tested for extracting 12 model organochlorine pesticides, including BHC, lindane, and
14 DDT, demonstrating high isolation efficiency. The coated thin film and its silylation modification
15 were characterized using standard spectroscopic techniques, confirming the successful creation of a
16 new adsorbent phase. The direct immersion SPME approach achieved relative recoveries ranging
17 from 65% to 99%, with reproducibility (RSD) below 6%. This method provided low detection limits
18 (10 to 15 ng L⁻¹) and quantitation limits (32 to 50 ng L⁻¹).

19 **Significance:** Our approach offers an eco-friendly, highly efficient solution for the extraction and
20 detection of trace organochlorine pesticides. The significant improvement in recovery rates and
21 reproducibility, combined with low detection and quantitation limits, underscores the potential of this
22 method to enhance analytical practices in environmental monitoring and public health. Furthermore,
23 the use of sustainable materials and processes aligns with global efforts to reduce environmental
24 impact in analytical chemistry.¹

¹ Abbreviations: MMT - Montmorillonite; NiTi - Nickel-Titanium; DI-SPME - Direct Immersion Solid Phase Microextraction; EDS - Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy; XPS - X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy; ATR-FTIR - Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy; HRXPS - High-Resolution XPS

1 **Keywords:** Solid Phase Microextraction, Montmorillonite Clay, Nickel-Titanium Alloy,
2 Organochlorine Pesticides, Green Chemistry, Water Analysis

3

4 **1. Introduction**

5 Sample preparation is often the bottleneck in the analytical process. Over the past three decades,
6 microextraction techniques have significantly advanced due to their ability to meet the main
7 objectives of sample preparation: analyte isolation, interference cleanup, and achieving high
8 enrichment factors, ideally all within a single step. SPME, developed by Arthur and Pawliszyn [1],
9 has become a powerful technique for determining chemical compounds in water samples at trace
10 levels. However, the fragility of conventional fibers presents challenges in adsorption and injection
11 processes. Recently, advancements in SPME [2] have aimed to develop new analytical methods that
12 minimize procedural steps and reduce potential errors. These innovations focus on creating
13 affordable, eco-friendly, and simple techniques for extracting molecules from various aqueous
14 matrices, particularly for analytes at trace levels, thus advancing green analytical chemistry.

15

16 The search for new "green" sorbents in alignment with Green Analytical Chemistry principles has
17 spurred the development of eco-friendly materials for extraction applications. Examples include cork
18 [3-5], clays [4,6-11], cotton [5], pollen [5], agricultural by-products [5], and biopolymers [8]. Clay is
19 abundantly available in nature and offers excellent adsorption properties due to its large surface area
20 ($50\text{-}200\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$). Its structure is primarily composed of quartz and metal oxides in a unique lamellar
21 configuration: a tetrahedral-octahedral-tetrahedral arrangement of aluminosilicate. This structure
22 facilitates the intercalation of cations, enhancing its cation exchange capacity.

23 Various methods have been employed to prepare clay films, including solvent casting, spin-coating,
24 layer-by-layer assembly, Langmuir-Blodgett, and electrophoretic deposition [12-13]. However,
25 controlling properties such as thickness, surface morphology, and crystal structure poses challenges,
26 as these attributes significantly depend on the chosen growth method.

1 The radiofrequency R.F. magnetron sputtering is a physical vapor deposition technique that utilizes a
2 magnetic field to coat various materials over a large area with strong adhesion and nanometric
3 precision. This method enables the deposition of thin films on substrates under high vacuum
4 conditions, ensuring high purity and cost efficiency. R.F. magnetron sputtering is particularly useful
5 for growing isolated semiconductors and metal thin films with excellent structural quality on diverse
6 substrate types, including amorphous (e.g., glass), polycrystalline, and crystalline (e.g., Si (001)).
7 These characteristics are crucial for applications in solar cells, optoelectronic devices, and SPME
8 fibers [14-15]. Control over the physical properties of the films, such as thickness, surface
9 morphology, and crystal structure, is achieved by adjusting the experimental conditions like substrate
10 temperature, working pressure, and power source target within a high vacuum environment ($\sim 10^{-6}$
11 Torr), effectively minimizing contamination and impurities.

12
13 Conventional SPME fibers used in analytical chemistry often lack reusability and renewability.
14 Principle 7 of the Green Sample Preparation principles from the AGREEprep tool [16] underscores
15 the importance of sustainable materials. In this context, clay emerges as a promising alternative due
16 to its excellent adsorption properties and eco-friendly nature. With its large surface area and unique
17 lamellar structure, clay enhances cation exchange capacity, providing a sustainable and efficient
18 solution for green analytical methods. Given its composition and the unique characteristics of its
19 enriched silicon and aluminum chemistry, clay is well-positioned to advance in this field as an eco-
20 friendly sorbent in analytical applications. Montmorillonite (MMT), a specific type of clay, is
21 particularly well-suited for these applications. The process of fabricating fibers coated with nano-
22 clay through R.F. magnetron sputtering for SPME applications is yet to be explored. To our
23 knowledge, the application of solid-phase MMT on nickel-titanium (NiTi) alloy using R.F.
24 magnetron sputtering in SPME has not been previously reported, highlighting a significant
25 opportunity for innovation in the development of new solid-phase materials.

1 The goal of this study is to prepare and evaluate a new eco-friendly sorbent coating for SPME,
2 utilizing an MMT clay thin film deposited by R.F. magnetron sputtering in a high vacuum
3 atmosphere onto an NiTi alloy substrate. After coating, the thin film underwent a silylation
4 modification, and the device was tested for the extraction of 12 organochlorine compounds from
5 water samples in direct immersion mode. These low-polarity organochlorine molecules, extensively
6 studied by our group [17-18], were selected as model analytes to showcase the effectiveness of this
7 technique. Despite the ban on organochlorine pesticides in many regions, their continued use in some
8 less-developed countries leads to significant environmental and health risks. Research has
9 consistently shown these compounds to be harmful to both human and animal health over short,
10 medium, and long terms [19-20]. The innovative use of a clay thin film deposited by R.F. magnetron
11 sputtering, combined with the silylation modification, aims to address these concerns by providing a
12 highly efficient and eco-friendly method (0.54 index by AgrePrep), and offers a cheaper and easier
13 way for detecting and isolating these hazardous compounds.

14 **2. Materials and methods**

15 **2.1 Reagents and standards**

16 High-purity standards (>99%) of 12 organochlorine compounds, specifically BHC, lindane,
17 heptachlor, aldrin, heptachlor epoxide, DDT, dieldrin, endrin, endosulfan sulphate, DDD, endrin
18 aldehyde and DDE, were procured from Aldrich. Stock solutions were prepared at a concentration of
19 approximately 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in isooctane, under gravimetric control. These solutions were further
20 diluted with ultrapure water (Type I) to prepare the working standards. Both stock and working
21 solutions were stored at 4 °C as per standard protocols. Drinking water samples were spiked with a
22 mixture of these pesticides, each at a concentration of 100 ng L^{-1} , for method validation. The same
23 samples were then used to apply the method.

24

1 2.2 Chromatographic conditions for GC-ECD and GC-MS

2 Chromatographic analysis was performed using an Agilent 6890 Gas Chromatograph equipped with
 3 a μ ECD detector (Wilmington, USA). The column employed was an Equity®-5 (30 m length, 0.32
 4 mm ID, 0.25 μ m film thickness) from Aldrich. The oven temperature was initially set at 150 °C and
 5 increased at a rate of 5 °C per minute to a final temperature of 290 °C, which was held for 10
 6 minutes. The injector was maintained at 250 °C, utilizing a splitless injection mode where the split
 7 valve was opened after 30 seconds. The carrier gas, hydrogen of 99.999% purity, was flowed at 1.0
 8 mL min⁻¹, and nitrogen (also 99.999% purity, supplied by Cryogas, Colombia) served as the
 9 auxiliary gas at a rate of 30 mL min⁻¹. For the analysis of real samples, a GC-MS system was
 10 required for the confirmation process using SIM mode. The GC-QP2010Plus Shimadzu
 11 chromatograph was used. The column used was J&W Scientific DB-5 MS (30 m length, 0.25 mm
 12 ID, 0.25 μ m film thickness), with the column oven initially set at 150 °C. The injection temperature
 13 was 280 °C, and the mode was splitless with a sampling time of 1.00 minute. Flow control was
 14 maintained under linear velocity conditions with a pressure of 92.4 kPa, total flow of 9.0 mL min⁻¹,
 15 and column flow of 1.00 mL min⁻¹ at 38.0 cm sec⁻¹. The temperature program began with a hold
 16 time of 1 minute at 150 °C, then increased at 5.00 °C min⁻¹ to 300 °C over 5.00 minutes, followed by
 17 an equilibrium time of 3.00 minutes. The ion source and interface temperatures were both set at 300
 18 °C, with a solvent delay time of 3.00 minutes. The SIM mode was segmented into five groups for
 19 targeted analysis (Table 1).

20

21 **Table 1.** Mass spectrometry ion monitoring programmed in SIM mode with a 0.3 second event time.

Group	Start Time/min	End Time/min	SIM m/z
1	3.00	12.53	181, 183, 219, 111
2	12.53	15.55	66, 263, 91, 79
3	15.55	17.33	212, 282, 284, 176
4	17.33	19.67	246, 248, 318, 316, 79, 81, 82, 77, 263, 67
5	19.67	23.00	272, 274, 239, 237, 235, 165, 212

1 **2.3 Characterization of clay**

2 The MMT clay was sourced from Bentominercol S.A., located in El Libano, Tolima, Colombia,
3 where their main mining operations are conducted. This material was pretreated as described in Ref.
4 [7]. A variety of techniques were utilized to characterize the adsorbent material, including Fourier
5 Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA),
6 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), zeta
7 potential analysis, and Brunauer-Emmett-Teller surface area analysis. FTIR analysis was carried out
8 according to the methodologies established in our previous works [4-7]. TGA was performed using a
9 Q500 instrument from TA Instruments (New Castle, DE, USA). SEM images were taken as per
10 procedures from prior studies [7], and the zeta potential was measured using a ZetaSizer from
11 Malvern Instruments (UK). Brunauer-Emmett-Teller surface area analysis was conducted using a
12 Sortometro Micrometrics, Model ASAP 2020 PLUS (Corston Bath, UK). X-ray photoelectron
13 spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were executed in an ultra-high vacuum ($\sim 10^{-9}$ Pa) using a Specs
14 brand X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (NAP-XPS) equipped with a PHOIBOS 150 1D-DLD
15 analyzer and a monochromatic Al-K α X-ray source (1486.7 eV, 13 kV, 100 W). The energy step size
16 was 1 eV for survey spectra and 0.1 eV for high-resolution spectra, with 20 cycles conducted for
17 each high-resolution spectrum and five for the survey spectra. Charge compensation was set to 1 eV
18 and 20 μ A, and the binding energy scale was calibrated using the C 1s photoelectron line at 284.6 eV
19 [21].

20

21 **2.4 Clay thin film over NiTi wire**

22 The graphical abstract GA illustrates the complete assembly of the lab-made SPME fiber coated with
23 a modified clay thin film. The clay thin films were deposited onto a NiTi alloy wire used as a
24 substrate via an R.F. magnetron sputtering system in an argon atmosphere, utilizing a high-purity
25 clay sputter target that was fabricated in-house. A specialized experimental setup was designed in our

1 laboratory to ensure the deposition of a homogeneous film on the surface of the nickel-titanium wire
2 (5 cm length x 50 μm diameter).

3 The films were deposited on a substrate (NiTi wire), which was initially degreased with acetone and
4 methanol in an ultrasonic bath for 15 minutes. The substrates were then rinsed in deionized water for
5 an additional 15 minutes. Prior to deposition, the growth chamber was evacuated to a high vacuum
6 ($\sim 1 \times 10^{-6}$ Torr) to remove contaminant gases. Argon gas was then introduced into the chamber until
7 the desired working pressure was achieved. The R.F. source was activated, generating plasma
8 between the target and the shutter. Once the plasma stabilized, the shutter was opened to commence
9 the deposition for a predetermined period at a previously set substrate temperature. Following the
10 deposition, the R.F. power and gas supply were turned off, and the system was allowed to cool down
11 to room temperature. The argon inlet flow rate was regulated by a flux mass controller calibrated for
12 argon gas, and the substrate temperature (400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) was monitored using a thermocouple embedded in
13 the substrate holder. The experimental conditions for the sputtering depositions are detailed in Ref.
14 [22], and the magnetron setup is illustrated in Table 2.

1 **Table 2.** Experimental conditions and Magnetron Sputtering setup.

Experimental conditions		Magnetron configuration
Base pressure	1.0 x10 ⁻⁶ Torr	
Working pressure (P)	5.0 x 10 ⁻³ Torr	
Temperature substrate (Ts)	400 °C	
R.F. Power Source	70 Watts	
Time growth	45 min	

2

3 **2.4.1 Clay thin film modification**

4 After coating the NiTi wire with the clay thin film, the wire underwent peroxidation in an acidic
5 medium using a piranha solution (H₂O₂/H₂SO₄ at a 1:3 ratio) at 60 °C in a thermal DQO reactor
6 [14,15]. Once the silanol and aluminol groups were formed [23], they reacted with N-methyl-N-
7 (trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide to produce a coating with low polar affinity dominated by
8 trimethylsilyl groups (see Figure GA).

9

10 **2.4.2 Clay thin film characterization**

11 The clay thin film was characterized using several techniques, including X-ray photoelectron
12 spectroscopy (XPS) and scanning electron microscopy with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
13 (SEM-EDS), applied directly to the NiTi wire. Additional techniques such as attenuated total
14 reflectance Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) and contact angle measurements
15 were conducted, with these analyses preferably performed using a planar model as suggested [14].

16

17 **2.5 Direct immersion SPME configuration**

18 The optimization of variables was conducted using a One-Factor-At-a-Time design, where the
19 working range or central point of selected critical conditions was determined based on the optimal
20 conditions identified in our previous studies [17,18]. These included a sample volume of 25 mL, a

1 30-minute extraction time, a 1% salting-out effect, a stirring speed of 300 rpm, an extraction
2 temperature of 60 °C, a desorption time of 15 minutes, and a desorption temperature of 250 °C.

3 **2.6 Real and synthetic samples**

4 For real samples, tap drinking water was collected in the laboratory. In the case of synthetic samples,
5 they were prepared by spiking tap water with target analytes at a concentration of 100 ng L⁻¹.

7 **3. Results and Discussion**

8 **3.1 Characterization of MMT**

9 Comprehensive information regarding the compositional, structural, thermal stability, and
10 morphological properties of MMT clay is presented in the supplementary material.

12 **3.2 Characterization of MMT clay thin film**

13 **3.2.1 XPS**

14 The surface chemical compositions of NiTi wire and a MMT/NiTi thin film were characterized using
15 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. This analysis, as depicted in Figure S1, revealed the presence of
16 Ti 2*p* and Ni 3*p* photoemission lines from the NiTi wire's surface, indicating the presence of
17 constituent elements of fiber's substrate. Figures S1a and S1b highlight the primary emission levels
18 of Ca 2*p*, O 1*s*, Ti 2*p*, and Ni 3*p*, accompanied by Auger peaks such as CKLL, OKLL, and NiLMM.
19 These spectra also displayed secondary structures like satellites, ghost peaks, and non-
20 monochromatic radiation effects. Furthermore, the survey spectra from Figure S1b showed additional
21 lines from Si 2*p*, Al 2*p*, and Ca core levels, which are attributed to the clay thin film, demonstrating
22 the effective deposition at 400 °C. Each elemental peak, meticulously analyzed and calibrated using
23 the carbon C 1*s* binding energy at 284.8 eV, validated the surface contamination primarily from air
24 exposure, as evidenced by core levels of oxygen and carbon. Figures S1c and S1d present the Ti 2*p*
25 spectra across the full range for both the NiTi wire and the clay thin film deposited on NiTi wire at
26 400 °C. The red line in Figure S1c indicates the deconvolution of the XPS spectra into two Gaussian

1 functions, identifying the main peak of Ti $2p_{3/2}$ and the secondary peak of Ti $2p_{1/2}$ at binding energies
2 of 457 and 462.6 eV, respectively, indicative of the Ti core level in the +4 oxidation state. The spin-
3 orbit splitting was noted to be $\Delta = 5.6$ eV, and the intensity ratio $I_{Ti1/2}/I_{Ti3/2} = 0.5$, aligning with values
4 documented in the literature [24]. The observed shift in binding energies to higher values suggests
5 the presence of oxides, such as TiO₂ and C-O. The Ti $2p$ signal from the clay films exhibited more
6 noise compared to the bare NiTi wire, attributed to the interference from the film's thickness. As
7 observed in Figures S1a and S1b, the Ni $2p$ core level signal was notably weak, preventing the
8 acquisition of a high-resolution XPS (HRXPS) spectrum.

9
10 Although the presence of silicon in NiTi wires is uncommon, other elements such as aluminum,
11 silicon, or fluorine may be introduced as unintended contaminants during the manufacturing or
12 polishing processes [25]. However, the intensity of the Si $2p$ peak observed from the NiTi wire is
13 minimal and not shown here, in contrast to the more pronounced Si $2p$ signal obtained from the clay
14 thin film. Figure S1e displays the Si $2p$ core level spectrum from the clay thin film coated on the
15 NiTi wire, where the peak at 101.6 eV likely corresponds to Si-O or SiO_x bonds, with potential
16 values ranging from Si at 99.8 eV to SiO₂ at 103.5 eV [26]. Figure S1f presents the HRXPS spectrum
17 of the Al $2p$ core level in the clay thin film on NiTi. The main peak at 75.76 eV is attributed to the Al
18 $2p_{3/2}$ core level [27], showing a 1.46 eV shift to higher energy compared to the Al $2p_{3/2}$ value in
19 Al₂O₃ (74.3 eV). However, binding energies ranging from 74.4 eV to 74.8 eV have been reported for
20 aluminum oxide films prepared by magnetron sputtering under different experimental conditions
21 [28]. Figure S1g displays the O $1s$ core level spectrum at 532.9 eV, which likely represents oxygen in
22 O-Si bonds. Binding energies ranging from 528 to 529 eV are typically attributed to metallic oxides,
23 specifically to AlO₂ [27]. Figure S1h illustrates the Ca $2p$ peaks in the MMT thin film, which exhibit
24 a doublet at 348.9 eV (Ca $2p_{3/2}$) and 352.6 eV (Ca $2p_{1/2}$) with a spin-orbit splitting of 3.69 eV. The
25 spectral shifts observed in figures S1e, S1g, and S1h, where the main levels of silicon, oxygen and
26 calcium are evident, indicate the successful integration of these elements into the matrix. This

1 integration is suggested by the shift to lower binding energies for the $2p_{1/2}$ and $2p_{3/2}$ levels, a known
2 effect accompanying increases in silicon and oxygen peaks and the emergence of calcium. These
3 shifts suggest the formation of the thin film, evidenced by a reduction in the nickel and titanium
4 signals and an increase in those of oxygen and silicon.

5

6 **3.2.2 SEM –EDS analysis**

7 SEM-EDS analysis was conducted to examine the surface morphology and elemental composition of
8 both the bare NiTi wire and a clay thin film deposited on the NiTi wire at 400 °C. Figure S2a and
9 S2b display the SEM images at a 20 μm scale and 40X magnification, along with the EDS analysis
10 spectra of both the bare NiTi wire and the clay-coated film. The EDS analysis revealed that the bare
11 NiTi consists of C (23.7%), Mg (7.1%), Al (7.1%), Ti (40.6%), and Ni (21.6%), while the clay film
12 comprises C (4.1%), O (15.7%), Mg (2.29%), Al (0.9%), and Si (1.90%). The variable qualitative
13 composition determined by EDS depends on the specific area analyzed. The detection of oxygen and
14 silicon elements confirms the formation of the clay thin film.

15

16 **3.3 Chemical reaction for modification of clay thin film**

17 The surface modification of the clay thin film via a silylation reaction was evaluated using EDS,
18 ATR-FTIR spectroscopy, and contact angle measurements employing the planar model RDSE, as
19 depicted in Figures S3 and S4.

20

21 **3.3.1 ATR-FTIR**

22 The ATR-FTIR spectra obtained from the planar model (stainless steel) are presented in Figure S3,
23 where is shown the FTIR spectra of modified and non modified thin clay film. Figure S3A highlights
24 the emergence of C-H stretch vibrations at the 2900-2800 cm^{-1} range (encircled in orange), indicative
25 of the incorporation of trimethyl groups during the silylation modification of the clay thin film.

1 3.3.2 EDS analysis

2 Elemental analysis by EDS spectroscopy was performed at each step of the modification process of
3 the clay thin film deposited by R.F. magnetron sputtering. The stages included peroxidation in an
4 acid medium and silylation with N-methyl-N-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide, depicted in Figure
5 S4. The analysis reveals the presence of silicon and aluminum, with an increase in oxygen levels
6 after the coating and peroxidation processes. Subsequently, there is a notable decrease in oxygen and
7 aluminum, alongside a reduction in the elements Ni and Ti. The presence of silicon and aluminum,
8 the increase and subsequent decrease in oxygen, and the reduction of Ni and Ti signals indicate that
9 the thin film successfully covers the NiTi substrate. The constancy of silicon levels, considering the
10 surface-focused measurements, further supports the successful derivatization of the thin film.

11

12 3.3.3 Contact angle measurement

13 Contact angle measurements were conducted on a stainless steel surface (1.76 cm²) coated with the
14 derivatized thin film. A total of 18 measurements were made across six sections of the surface. The
15 average contact angle was determined to be 100 degrees, suggesting a hydrophobic surface, which
16 confirms the occurrence of the derivatization reaction. Figure S5 illustrates the non-polar nature of
17 the modified clay thin film, which shows a greater affinity for non-polar molecules such as the
18 targeted organochlorine compounds.

19

1 **3.4 Optimization of direct immersion SPME with new clay coating**

2 To optimize the critical variables in the microextraction process of the device, a One-Factor-At-a-
3 Time experimental design of type N + (N-1) [29-30] was utilized, featuring four control variables,
4 each tested at three levels. This approach enabled the conduct of up to 9 experiments, with at least
5 three replicates each, to establish the most effective operating conditions. The extraction parameters
6 were adapted from optimal conditions reported in the literature and adjusted within the system's
7 capabilities. Variables adjusted included the stirring rate, extraction time, temperature, and NaCl
8 concentration.

10 **3.4.1 Extraction time effect**

11 Extraction times of 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40 minutes were evaluated for the pesticide mixture,
12 consistently showing that durations of 30 and 40 minutes typically yielded the best results, as they
13 reached extraction equilibrium (Fig. 1).

14 <<Figure 1>>

15 **3.4.2 Stirring rate effect**

16 Stirring rates of 200, 300, 400, 500, and 700 rpm were evaluated. As demonstrated in Figure 2, the
17 optimal stirring rate for this system is 300 rpm. At rates higher than 300 rpm and because a low
18 sample volume was used, significant disturbance waves are produced, resulting in the loss of some
19 extracted analytes from the thin clay film.

20 <<Figure 2>>

21 **3.4.3 Extraction temperature effect**

22 Extractions were conducted at temperatures of 50 °C, 55 °C, 60 °C, 65 °C, and 70 °C. At 60 °C, no
23 significant changes in extraction efficiency were observed for most compounds compared to 50 °C,
24 establishing 60 °C as the optimal temperature. Increasing the temperature to 70 °C resulted in
25 significant changes, suggesting that the sorption of organochlorine compounds on the clay thin film
26 may be exothermic. This observation is illustrated in Figure 3.

1

2

<<Figure 3>>

3 3.4.4 Effect of NaCl addition

4 To explore the salting-out effect, salt concentrations of 0.5%, 1%, 2.5%, 5%, and 10% NaCl were
5 tested. It was found that a 1% NaCl concentration yielded consistent results due to more effective
6 analyte extraction. Higher concentrations of NaCl likely increase the sample's viscosity, which
7 hinders the mass transfer of analytes, as illustrated in Figure 4.

8

<<Figure 4>>

9 3.5 Analytical characteristics of the new developed SPME method

10 The analytical performance of the newly developed SPME method with MMT clay coated fibers is
11 detailed in Table 3. The analysis, conducted with six replicates (n=6), consistently showed an RSD
12 below 7.5%. The LOD ranged from 10 ng L⁻¹ to 15 ng L⁻¹, and relative recovery rates varied from
13 65% to 99%, which are considered exceptionally high for an equilibrium-based extraction technique
14 like SPME. These outcomes are equiparable those of alternative SPME methods using different
15 coating materials such as cork [31], metal-organic framework MIL-101 [32,34,36], graphene [33,35],
16 carbonized polydopamine [34], and traditional SPME fibers [31-34,37].

1 **Table 3.** Detailed analytical performance of the novel SPME method with the green MMT coated
 2 NiTi fibers.

Molecule	Linear Range ng L ⁻¹	R ²	LOD ng L ⁻¹	LOQ ng L ⁻¹	RSD %	EF	Recovery %	LODs other methods (ng L ⁻¹)					
								Carboniz- ed polydopa- mine coupled with GC- MS [34]	Graphene fiber coupled with GC- ECD [35]	Graphene fiber coupled with GC- MS [33]	MOF- 199/ GO fiber coupled with GC- ECD [36]	PDMS fiber coupled with GC- ITMS-MS [37]	
BHC	33-1000	0.9928	10	33	3.6	656	95.3						
Lindane	41-1000	0.9980	12	41	3.7	33	86.7						16
Heptachlor	50-1000	0.9970	15	50	1.4	124	65.2	15		18			22
Aldrin	33-1000	0.9968	10	33	1.0	789	65.4	9		9		3	5
Heptachlor epoxide	39-1000	0.9971	12	39	1.4	305	93.3	11				4	5
DDT	33-1000	0.9956	10	33	3.6	554	89.1	2	5	0.2			26
Dieldrin	35-1000	0.9956	11	35	5.0	269	64.8	5				5	9
Endrin	40-1000	0.9976	12	40	6.2	317	78.4						
Endosulfan sulphate	35-1000	0.9967	11	35	5.7	66	99.1					5	
DDD	50-1000	0.9979	15	50	2.5	86	93.8	8	2			3	8
Endrin aldehyde	39-1000	0.9979	12	39	3.7	254	80.5						
DDE	37-1000	0.9976	11	37	7.5	452	93.3		1			3	1

3
 4 As shown in Table 3, the system provides robust analytical performance for extracting
 5 organochlorine compounds in direct injection mode from aqueous samples, offering high recovery
 6 and enrichment factors. This method represents a viable alternative to traditional SPME coatings, as
 7 demonstrated in other studies [33-39] (Fig. 5)

8 <<Figure 5>>

9 3.6 Analysis of drinking water samples using the new developed SPME method

10 Three samples of drinking water were analyzed for organochlorine compounds using the new SPME
 11 method with the MMT/NiTi thin film. The concentrations of the compounds were found to be below
 12 LOD. To further investigate, these drinking water samples, as well as water samples spiked with
 13 organochlorine compounds, were analyzed using GC-MS in SIM mode (Fig. 6).

<<Figure 6>>

4. Conclusions

This study introduces, for the first time, the application of a green sorbent thin film, MMT clay, deposited on a NiTi alloy wire using R.F. magnetron sputtering, subsequently modified by silylation to alter the adsorbent's polarity for extracting low-polarity molecules such as organochlorine compounds via SPME in direct immersion mode. The microextraction technique demonstrated an adequate LOD in the range of 10-15 ng L⁻¹, with significant relative recovery rates of the analytes ranging from 65% to 99%. Effective preconditioning of the system is crucial to match the performance of other green coatings. The modified MMT clay thin film, applied to the NiTi alloy wire of the SPME device, exemplifies a new green coating approach, adhering to the principles of green chemistry. MMT, a widely used, stable, and robust eco-material, facilitates the extraction process with minimal use of organic solvents.

The successful application of this green sorbent thin film highlights the potential for eco-friendly materials in analytical chemistry, promoting sustainability in sample preparation techniques. This innovative approach not only reduces the environmental impact by minimizing the use of harmful organic solvents but also offers a cost-effective and efficient alternative for trace analysis of low-polarity compounds. Furthermore, the versatility of the modified MMT thin film could inspire future research and development of other green sorbents tailored for various analytical applications. This work underscores the importance of integrating green chemistry principles in analytical methodologies, paving the way for more sustainable and environmentally conscious scientific practices.

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8

9 **Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted Technologies in the Writing Process**

10 During the preparation of this work, the editor, Esmée Joosten, used ChatGPT by OpenAI to assist in
11 refining the language, checking consistency in citations, and providing guidance on formatting as
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14

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1 **Figure and table captions**

2 **Figure 1.** Optimization of extraction time in DI-SPME for targeting organochlorine
3 compounds in water samples, highlighting the most effective durations for achieving
4 equilibrium.

5 **Figure 2.** Effect of stirring rate on the extraction of organochlorine compounds from
6 water samples using DI-SPME, highlighting the optimal rate at 300 rpm to minimize
7 disturbance and analyte loss.

8 **Figure 3.** Impact of extraction temperature on the efficiency of extracting
9 organochlorine compounds using DI-SPME, with 60 °C identified as the optimal
10 temperature.

11 **Figure 4.** Optimization of the DI-SPME extraction process for target organochlorine
12 compounds in water samples under varying salting-out conditions.

13 **Figure 5.** Chromatogram of a spiked sample at 100 ng L⁻¹ solution of OCs mix in a DI-
14 SPME setup extracting organochlorine compounds using a modified clay thin film
15 coated over an NiTi wire.

16 **Figure 6.** Total Ion Chromatogram (TIC) of a tap drinking water (A) and spiked
17 drinking water at 100 (B) ng L⁻¹. The chromatograms were obtained with GC-MS in
18 SIM mode, and the extraction was performed by the new DI-SPME configuration with a
19 modified MMT clay thin film coated over an NiTi wire.

20 **Table 1.** Mass Spectrometry ion monitoring programmed in SIM mode with a 0.3
21 second event time.

22 **Table 2.** Experimental conditions and Magnetron Sputtering setup.

23 **Table 3.** Detailed analytical performance of the novel SPME method with the green
24 MMT coated NiTi fibers.

1 Highlights:

2

3 1. Novel SPME fibers coated with a clay thin film are eco-friendly and highly
4 efficient

5

6 2. The clay sputter target used as the coating is sustainable material in line with
7 green chemistry principles

8

9 3. The lab-made SPME fibers developed here represent a green sample
10 preparation technology

11

Journal Pre-proof

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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